

A study on the Strategies to Reduce Employee Absenteeism

Nishtha*

Department of University School of Business, Chandigarh University, Gharuan, Mohali, 140412

Dr. Mini AmitArrawatia

Faculty of Management and Humanities, JayotiVidyapeeth University, Jaipur

Nishthaverma08@gmail.com, miniमितarrawatia05@gmail.com

Abstract

Absenteeism generally refers to the spontaneous absence of an employee from the work. It also acts as a routine pattern of an employee to remain absent from a duty. It always acts as a barrier for any kind of organization as it will have an effect on the growth of the organization. Human resource is a significant part without which the organization cannot be imagined. Absenteeism refers to employee absence from the work or duty because of several reasons such as absence due to illness, social functions, personal reasons etc. Employee absenteeism is normal but when this ratio rises it will directly result on the performance of an employee as well as increases the organization workload and cost also.

OBJECTIVE : The objective of the study is to reduce business costs, control on absence acts by forming various effective strategies to gain highest form of productivity and efficiency. As there is a lot of competitive pressure in the environment, the companies cannot afford these excessive absences. Hence, numerous companies are concentrating on eliminating or reducing this issue. Absence of employee results in various revenue losses and lost productivity annually. There are numerous consequences that are faced by the organizations due to high levels of work absences; the organization should form strategies to manage the level of absence in order to support the growth and sustainability of the organization.

METHOD/STATISTICAL TOOL: Secondary data is used to do study about absenteeism and strategies to reduce it.

FINDINGS: The study shows that absenteeism increases cost of the organization. Training method and absence monitoring method can be used to reduce the absenteeism.

Keywords— *Absenteeism, Employees absenteeism, Organization success and productivity.*

Introduction

Every organization succeeds because of its valuable assets i.e. employees. Hence, employee's absenteeism acts as a key obstacle for business success. Absenteeism causes harm to the organization's production process. Thus it is must to control this absenteeism situation, by a detailed

and thorough analysis to recognize the serious causes of absenteeism that help in creating a healthy Organizational Culture. It is also termed as the worker's failure to report on job when the work or job is scheduled for him. Absenteeism on reason of lockout, layoff, strikes or suspension is not considered into account. Hence, it is only related to voluntary absenteeism that can be on the basis of their personal motives.

Definition

There is no standard definition of employee absenteeism. As per French Man, "Absenteeism takes place whenever an individual selects to allot their time to those events that compete with planned job or work. It is an outline where an employee is regularly absent from his job or work. It can also be termed as an employees' failure to report for job when they are planned to do that work. According to Martocchio & Harrison, Absenteeism refers to lack of an employees' physical existence at a particular place and time when they are socially expected to be there.

"Absence measurement" is crucial for most of the organizations as they try to avoid it and keep this to a minimum. Absence measurement is difficult to recognize the diverse patterns for employee's absenteeism as well as it targets the variables that affects it. Employers always expect consistent ongoing attendance from their staffs. Poor attendance of an employee becomes a major problem for the employer. It is essential to maintain a proactive program for addressing and handling absenteeism.

Every organization works with the motive of having less cost with more profit. Investment is done by the organization on their employees so that they can generate income to the organization in return. But absenteeism acts as a barrier which gives reverse outcome on the organizations' productivity. Every employee works in a hierarchy where they have their own duty in the organization so employee absenteeism acts as a hurdle on this hierarchy which results in the negative effect on the level of productivity. Absenteeism is one of the difficult problems that need to be tackled, as there can be both genuine and poor excuses for absence. Therefore, it will be a challenge for the employers to efficiently monitor, control and decrease the level of absenteeism as well as increase the productivity.

Literature review

According to Luthans (1995), there is a constant contrary relationship between absenteeism and job satisfaction, i.e. when the level of job satisfaction is high, the level of absenteeism seems to be low whereas when the level of satisfaction is low, the level of absenteeism seems to be high. According to Robbins (1998); Robbins, Odendaal & Roodt (2003); Spector (1997), it has been found that dissatisfied employees seem to miss work, absenteeism is a complex variable which is influenced by various factors. Steers et al. (1996) supported the concept that dissatisfied employees along with several job aspects are more likely to remain absent. Cole and Kleiner (1992) specified that employee absence not just results into loss of productivity but acts as a loss for the organization where the cost of employee benefit still runs even if the employee remains absent from the work. Johns and Nicholson (1982) described employee absence as a workplace problem that needs to be solved. Over the last many years, scholars have tried to expose the difficulty and multiplicity of absence behaviour. Martocchio and Harrison (1993) consider that absenteeism needs to be witnessed as more of a result than behaviour. There are endless lists of probable causes of absenteeism such as trouble

related to transportation; illness, job frustrations, work-life imbalance, childcare duties, eldercare duties, other domestic responsibilities, etc. are few of the reasons of employee absence.

Statement of problem

Absenteeism is one of the major problems in almost every organization. Higher absenteeism creates a significant cost to the business even in the case when the absent employee does not receive any pay. Due to disorganization of work, work schedules result into delays that act as a management failure in order to meet the dates of delivery. Generally, proper working conditions, acceptable salary, leave for rest, etc. create the most effective method of minimizing the cost of absenteeism. Despite of improving the working conditions, there is still a problem of absenteeism.

Objective of the study

- To find out various reasons for employee absenteeism.
- To study the causes and effects of employee absenteeism.
- To study the measures to control absenteeism.

Research Methodology

Data collection

The present study requires the use of secondary data. The necessary data has been collected from the published research or articles from several journals.

Data Interpretation

As per the first objectives, there are various reasons of absenteeism. The occurrence of absenteeism has been described in numerous ways. The environment prevailing in an organization affects the attitude of the employee towards his work. It can either induce him to be present regularly in the organization or retains him away. Ambiguity, irregularity, and misunderstanding in the organization are seen to be significant reasons of absenteeism. The practice and approach of the management also results into absenteeism.

As per the second objective, various causes of absenteeism have been studied which are:

- Disturbance or instability with the organization conditions.
- Workplace fatigue.
- Unhealthy working environment.
- Lack of satisfactory welfare facilities.
- Inappropriate and unrealistic employees' policies.
- Insufficient facility of leave.
- Harassment.
- Stress, Burnout and low morale.
- Employee Disengagement.

- Continuous illness.
- Job hunting.

According to the third objective, the measures to control the level of absenteeism have been studied and these measures are:

- Acceptance of a well- definite procedure of recruitment.
- Friendly relationship between employers and employees.
- Facility of reasonable salary and benefits as well as job security for employees.
- Employee motivation and social measures.
- Better communication and quick redressal of grievances.
- Generous grant for leave.

Findings

- Employees' absenteeism results in the increase in cost and decline in productivity of the organization.
- Employees just to take extra leave because of illness or stress or any other disease.
- Training methods or absence monitoring system should be used for reducing employee's absenteeism.

Suggestions and Recommendations

- The finest and simplest method to decrease the level of absenteeism is by providing counseling to the employees who used to take unnecessary leaves as well as make them aware about the absenteeism problems.
- One of the actual ways of dealing with the problem of absenteeism is by liberalizing the rules regarding leave. The organization's strict approach towards granting leave even during the genuine case allures the employee to go on leave still on loss of pay.
- The rules and guidelines related to attendance should be clarified to the employees. Sufficient number of employees should be there in the organization to reduce the work load. This will help the existing employees to work better without any stress and this will reduce the level of absenteeism.
- Free check-ups through periodical medical camps can improve employees' health. This will reduce the level of absenteeism.
- Welfare measures should be improved which will considerably reduce absenteeism.
- Severe disciplinary methods should be used to reduce absenteeism.

Conclusion

This research study about the problem of employees' absenteeism and explores the preventive and corrective arrangements. There are various programs that can be applied exclusively or mutually in order to reduce the level of absenteeism in an organization. Employee absenteeism is a costly and serious issue being faced by the organizations throughout the world. This issue wants that all the employees must recognize the consequences of such behaviour from an organizations' viewpoint and from the personal viewpoint.

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